

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. CARLOS L. ELLOREG JR.

Associate Professor I

Negros Oriental State University

carlos.ellorej@norsu.edu.ph

“ROOTS OF SACRIFICE, FRUITS OF GRACE: MY JOURNEY FROM FARM TO FACULTY”

I am Carlos Lozano Ellore Jr. I was born into a world where simplicity and struggle walked hand-in-hand. Our family belongs to the lower-income sector of society, surviving through the hard work of our hands—farming, raising livestock, and working under larger landowners. My parents, both having finished only up to sixth grade, poured their strength not into titles or degrees, but into fields and labor, just to put food on our table. We have no permanent homes. We had dreams but they were often placed second to survival.

As the eldest son in our family, I was trained early to work with my father in a physically demanding job. At the age of six, I was already cooking for my younger siblings and taking on responsibilities far beyond my years when my parents were working. It was not always easy, but it taught me about resilience.

Despite the financial challenges, my parents believed in education. I started school at Basak Elementary School in Zamboanguita, Negros Oriental, up to grade five, and then transferred to Mayana Elementary School in Jagna, Bohol for my final year. I continued my high school studies at San Miguel Academy, and later at Jehovah Jireh School in Zamboanga City, where I was blessed to be supported by my aunt, my mother’s younger sister, who took me in and allowed me to continue studying.

After high school, I pursued a two-year associate of industrial technology (AIT) major in Electronics Technology at Central Visayas Polytechnic College (CVPC) for the plan in preparation for application to the Philippine Navy. However, my father also had other plans. He believed I had more to offer and convinced me to pursue a four-year degree, Bachelor of Science in Industrial Technology (BSIT) in Electronics Technology, which required an additional two years (one year of study and one year of on-the-job training).

Together, we have worked hard to make this dream possible. My father continued farming, and I began earning by repairing electronic appliances. We lived daily, working not just for survival anymore but for a better future.

After completing my degree, I worked in several private companies as technicians in electronics repair shop, a line-man, and a head-end operator in a cable TV company. Then, in a twist of fate I never saw coming, I was recommended and hired as a faculty member in the college where I graduated, now known as Negros Oriental State University (NORSU). I replaced my third-year professor with our major course after he retired.

That was in 2002. I have been in service since then.

Looking back, I see not just a life of hardship but a life full of purpose and blessings. I may not have had the comfort of wealth, but I was rich in lessons, strength, and love from my family. God has been good.

To this day, my children are not fully aware of the depth of my journey. That is why I share this—not for recognition but for inspiration. I want to encourage youth who are struggling.

“Your beginnings do not define your destiny; what matters is your hard work, your willingness to learn, your belief in yourself, and your determination to never give up.”

Whatever your background may be, if you are willing to sacrifice, serve, and strive, you too can harvest the fruits of grace.

